

ADVANTAGES OF USING GAMIFICATION IN COMPUTER SCIENCE AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article describes the advantages and disadvantages of using gamification in teaching computer science and information technology. The educational process discusses the impact of using various gaming technologies on the educational process.

Key Words: information and communication technologies, interactive education, gaming technologies, gamification, cognitive, game concept, web quests.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, information and communication technologies and interactive education are firmly integrated into the educational process. There are many innovative educational technologies available, but most of them fit into the traditional classroom system. The essence of teaching methods remains the same: the teacher is the source of information, students are the recipients of information. Only the conditions and forms change. But does all this meet the interests of modern society and the education system?

MAIN PART

The relevance of this topic lies in the fact that if previously the teacher was higher than the student in terms of development and competence, now the teacher often lags behind children who have intuitively mastered new technologies and

become firmly entrenched in their consciousness. Therefore, a problem arises - the teacher is not modern, he is divorced from the modern world. Passive use of modern educational technologies in the classroom and lack of ICT proficiency lead to children's lack of confidence in school and loss of interest in learning. Speak with students in the same language and communicate with them in the same information space at school, that is, teachers now have no choice but to adapt and actively use innovative educational technologies. And in order for the learning to be colorful and meet the interests of students, its elements are gamified, that is, continuous feedback is created with students through a game that gradually introduces the topic without losing focus.

Involving games in the educational process is not something new, but the introduction of information and communication technologies makes it possible to expand games, game forms and elements in the classroom. A new term has appeared in the practice of modern education - "gamification", which is defined as the use of game elements and game design methods in non-game contexts: application of approaches specific to computer games in software for non-game processes.

The term "gamification" is often confused with other game-related concepts. It should be noted that gamification is not immersion in a three-dimensional virtual world, not games in the educational process, and not necessarily in digital format. This is just an auxiliary tool to increase cognitive activity, participation and motivation.

Through play, students begin to develop skills that they tend to ignore or resist developing. Gamification facilitates learning and becomes a natural form of organizing the educational activities of modern people. The principle of gamification means that the introduction of elements from other areas (games, social networks)

into the learning process allows us to create a more comfortable environment for students.

Play is a very flexible form of learning. It involves modeling situations corresponding to the implementation of real actions within the framework of the proposed model. As a result, we have stronger student learning. In addition, the learning process is self-motivated - the better a person understands a certain topic, the more interesting it is to him. Therefore, the game form of classes acts as a means of stimulating and motivating learning activities.

Basic principles of the game:

1. The voluntary nature of the game. Voluntary participation, the willingness of players to participate, is an important gaming principle. This is a particularly important and complex rule for schools.

2. Choice in the game. The decisions of the participants influence the course of the next game. Choice gives you a sense of control, freedom, and makes you fully engaged in the game. If there is no choice, the game will not work. When it comes to gamification, it's important to keep choice for participants.

3. Game algorithms. When you give participants choices, you need to understand how they will achieve their goals. It is necessary to calculate these paths and estimate their specific gravity. A simple example: having collected N shopping chips in a supermarket, you can buy 5 small items or one large item. Or, in a math search, an example might be worth 5 points, but a difficult problem might be worth 30 points.

4. Feedback. No game is possible without feedback. The participant makes a choice and receives an answer. Feedback is important in any game. Constant feedback in a useful or interesting form (for example, in the form of

an infographic) can motivate you to be active. For example, when the on-board computer shows a certain speed, pedal faster or take the same number of steps as yesterday, etc.

5. Unexpected pleasant comments (rewards). This mechanism is constantly used in various video games. Participants will be attracted and involved in the game when they unexpectedly receive their achievements and rewards that they did not expect. Research within the framework of behaviorism theory shows that the most effective mechanism for reinforcing desired behavior is variation. Open any game: from the first minutes they will show you how many words you remember, your steps and what kind of person you are. A holiday only for feedback: ratings, titles, fame.

There are two types of gamification: content and structure.

Content gamification is changing the content of what you do, adding game elements to ordinary processes to make them more playful. For example, a regular test can turn into a final battle with a boss (teacher), like in an online game.

Structured gamification is the use of game elements (stickers, bonus points, etc.) to make learning content easier and more fun for the learner. The main thing is that the student understands why he received the award. It is necessary to encourage not only good work, but also, for example, a new skill.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

How to introduce a game in the classroom? To start, you can offer students an experience, discuss the length of the experience, and emphasize the importance of feedback. High school students can participate in the development itself, and they can use the experience of children participating in various online games. It is very important to define your mission. Want to teach your kids how to work as a team? Want to reduce your fear of speaking on the board? There should be one task and it

should be formulated as precisely as possible. Next, you should design the game and choose a scoring system that works for your students. It is better to avoid the school five-point system and calculating the arithmetic average - it has its place. You should try to create a sense of progression, like in games. The player must clearly understand how many points he can get and why. Then the guys have drive, because they themselves influence the result. For example, 150 points plus 300 extra points, 50 bonus points.... Bingo! You are in the first thousand!

Topics can be divided into levels. If the teacher understands the logic of the curriculum (what to teach first, what to teach later; what is more difficult, what is easier), then children do not always understand why one or another section follows another. Themes can be expressed in terms of levels. Then the students will understand: in order to move to the next stage, they must first complete the previous one.

Creating resources for the game:

Write instructions. You can write the instructions on paper or record them on an electronic device. It explains how to get certain points and overcome certain obstacles.

Organization of teams. With the advent of the team, the main element of the game is added to learning - constant feedback (feedback). Children need to be taught how they can support each other in their development. For example, they can help with constructive criticism.

The easiest way to practice gamification in computer classes is to create educational quests, web quests, various tasks using programs, applications, etc. Below is a table of correspondence between activities and game concepts, in which you can find game concepts corresponding to various types of activities.

The benefits of gamification in the learning process are obvious:

the student's genuine interest, his involvement in the process, including the most “boring” lessons. Unlike traditional forms of learning, games include a very important component – entertainment.

the mental processes of the game participants are activated: attention, understanding, interest, perception, thinking.

an excellent way to form and master current competencies: organizational and communicative (team work, communication, influence on a partner, negotiations, conversations, observation, etc.), personal (self-awareness, self-management), cognitive (goal setting), planning, correction, analysis, reflection).

Currently, various game-based learning resources allow students to use them taking into account the age characteristics, interests, skills and knowledge level of students.

CONCLUSION

Games as a means of effective cooperation between teachers and students can better develop children’s communication skills, increase motivation, provide modern practical knowledge and abandon the outdated testing system. The ultimate success of such technologies depends on how well innovation addresses the challenges of overcoming the shortcomings of the educational system and meeting the ever-increasing needs of society, as well as ensuring the positive impact of "gamification". Playful methods can make students want to learn again. If you harness the energy, motivation, and potential of games and help students learn, you can give them the tools they need to succeed in real life.

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